

Army SATCOM On The Move Technology Initiatives

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ABSTRACT

The Army is increasingly reliant on Beyond Line of Sight (BLOS) communications due to a non-contiguous battlefield. The Warfighter also requires mobility and network connectivity to provide the needed level of near real-time, tactically-relevant information. On-the-move (OTM) space based communications forms a critical layer in supporting these essential networking capabilities.

There are a significant number of inter-related technical hurdles involved in developing satellite communications (SATCOM) OTM systems. Size, weight, and power (SWaP) are limited on tactical vehicles. There are many tactical vehicles in the Army inventory, used differently by different units, representing diverse integration issues and challenges. Required data rates need to be supported within size and power restrictions, driving higher antenna and radio frequency (RF) performance. Ground communications are required in a high velocity, high acceleration, high blockage, cross country environment, driving rigorous pointing requirements. Systems need to be designed to work with current and planned military satellites in their respective frequency bands, which typically drives state-of-the-art. Electronic jamming protection and extremely low profile need to be considered in order to maintain communications and avoid visual targeting of the host tactical vehicle.

Space and Terrestrial Communications Directorate (STCD) Space Systems Division has been analyzing and addressing the technology to support required satellite communications (SATCOM) OTM system performance. Successful research and develop initiatives will be discussed, as well as planned initiatives to support future efforts addressing advanced requirements and future Military SATCOM systems at Extremely High Frequency (EHF). Specific component technologies and how they fit into meeting overall system objectives will be included. Lastly, the transition of these technologies to the tactical Army will be addressed.

TECHNICAL HURDLES

There are a significant number of inter-related technical hurdles involved in developing satellite communications (SATCOM) OTM systems.

Ground communications are required in a harsh, high velocity, high acceleration, high blockage, cross country environment, driving rigorous pointing requirements. The currently applicable standard for the Army cross country environment is the Churchville B course located at the Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD. This requires accommodating angular accelerations typically on the order of 500 deg/sec². Table 1 shows maximum angular accelerations and velocities measured around three axes (z down, x forward, y right). This data represents one test series for different courses at APG [1].

Vehicle	Course	Maximum [Angular Velocity] (deg/s)			Maximum [Angular Accel] (deg/s ²)		
		x	y	z	x	y	z
M1113 HMMWV	Churchville B	14.8	76.6	32.6	209.4	568.7	76.3
	Perryman 3	27.5	57.5	23.7	237.5	397.1	96.5
	Belgian Block	30.0	30.6	22.1	441.2	414.5	115.8
M1152 HMMWV	Churchville B	14.5	37.9	31.8	182.3	301.6	100.0
	Perryman 3	46.8	58.2	22.5	504.1	407.3	131.0
	Belgian Block	39.9	31.4	20.9	598.4	394.1	135.5
	Imbedded Rock	16.2	19.8	11.8	301.8	353.0	166.6

Table 1. Maximum Angular Velocities and Accelerations.

Antenna beamwidth, driven by performance requirements, also impacts pointing requirements. Tactical Army systems typically require SATCOM OTM data rates of 512 kbps. As antenna gain is increased to support required rates, beamwidth decreases and pointing requirements become more demanding. Vehicle characteristics also contribute to pointing requirements because accelerations experienced by the SATCOM OTM system are dependent on the location on the vehicle and vehicle characteristics such as suspension stiffness. Pointing requirements drive system components, such as Inertial Navigation System (INS) accuracy and azimuth/elevation motor size for mechanical SATCOM OTM systems. This creates a performance vs. size, weight, and power (SWaP) challenge on tactical vehicles. This issue is compounded if unique

military frequency bands or multiple frequency bands need to be supported. The Wideband Global System (WGS) satellite constellation, which operates at X and K/Ka bands, is a current focus for SATCOM OTM systems, as is the K/Q band to support protected OTM operation on the Advanced Extremely High Frequency (AEHF) constellation.

Maximizing antenna performance within available SWaP makes cooling a significant issue. SATCOM OTM systems are required to be covered in a radome, restricting air flow. One potential or partial solution is increasing the power added efficiency of the power amplifier, typically the major heat contributor. Increasing efficiency decreases heat required to be dissipated. This drives state of the art, especially at military frequency bands, and can increase cost. Additionally, novel cooling approaches such as liquid cooled systems are being explored to minimize complexity and cost.

The high blockage cross country environment also drives the type of tracking required for SATCOM OTM systems. Closed loop tracking in at-the-halt (ATH) SATCOM systems is generally implemented when the beamwidth is small compared to satellite motion. Closed loop allows the use of continual updates from a receive signal or beacon to modify the positioning of the ground antenna boresight. However, blockages encountered while OTM disrupt and skew the closed loop process. Approaches such as open loop pointing with periodic closed loop updates and carefully designed algorithms to deal with the contingencies of an OTM system have been investigated. Specific solutions and selection of closed/open/hybrid approaches require trading performance versus cost for a given system. In the case of specialized SATCOM systems, such as frequency hopping systems, feedback from the modem may be required in order to provide closed loop updates. All of this contributes to the complexity of SATCOM OTM systems. Figure 1 shows the interactions of some of the relevant SATCOM OTM trade characteristics and requirements. For example, severity of pointing requirements will drive SWaP and cost by affecting the accuracy of the Inertial Navigation System (INS) required and motor sizes for mechanical antenna implementations.

All of these issues and complexities driven by OTM requirements can drive cost. Particular cost drivers include pointing, frequency bands, and reduced SWaP requirements. Cost needs to be considered as a trade parameter during design.

Figure 1. SATCOM OTM Characteristics/Requirements Interaction

TECHNOLOGY EFFORTS

A. EHF/Milstar On the Move

An initial effort to develop and demonstrate an on-the-move terminal based on the Milstar Low Data Rate (LDR) waveform met all of these goals. The 44 GHz uplink frequency and a 12” antenna gave a tight pointing accuracy requirement while avoiding potential regulatory issues. Initial analysis of the baseband issues was examined in detail by MIT Lincoln Laboratory (MIT-LL) [2]. The Extremely High Frequency (EHF) OTM antenna was built by Harris Corporation, with some radio frequency components from MIT-LL. This was a three-axis antenna, out of concern for the “keyhole” problem, where OTM pointing for a two axis antenna at zenith requires impossibly high angular accelerations. The Milstar OTM terminal was used in a number of experiments to investigate timing, protocol and blockage issues in a number of environments [3, 4, 5, 6]. A demonstration of the terminal at Fort Monmouth, NJ in June 2002 proved to the community that EHF SATCOM OTM was technically feasible.

Based on this success, STCD and PM Warfighter Information Network – Tactical (WIN-T) partnered to develop a Ka-band OTM antenna for use on the Wideband Global SATCOM (WGS) constellation to provide an OTM capability for PM WIN-T’s Ka-Band SATCOM Augmentation Terminal (KaSAT). The initial concept was to develop a very low-profile antenna, but in dialog with vehicle programs, PM WIN-T discovered that area is at a great premium on tactical vehicles. This discussion changed the antenna specifications by significantly reducing the available antenna base area. The resulting contract with Titan/Datron (now part of L3 Communications) was to develop a three-axis Ka-band

OTM antenna with a 12” aperture. Though the antenna development was successful, there was a several year delay in the launch of the first WGS satellite. On their own, L3/Datron developed this Ka-band antenna into a very successful Ku-band product line. Figure 2 shows the Titan/Datron Ka-band OTM antenna.

Figure 2, Ka-OTM antenna

In parallel with the OTM terminal efforts, STCD also contracted with Boeing Phantom Works to investigate the issues, performance and mitigations of transmitting Internet Protocol (IP) traffic over a SATCOM OTM link [7, 8, 9]. This effort leveraged significant investment Boeing had made in their planned Connexion airborne IP service, as well as some other IRaD projects. Recognizing that a small number of cooperating OTM terminals with high-band terrestrial connectivity could significantly reduce the re-transmit delay for missed packets, STCD entered into a Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) contract with Fantastic Data. Fantastic Data was able to develop and demonstrate a protocol that takes advantage of a common satellite footprint to enable cooperating OTM terminals to fill in missed packets at any one OTM terminal in terrestrial transmission times, rather than in satellite round trip delays, while greatly increasing overall end-to-end performance and reliability [10].

B. Affordable Directional Antenna and Pointing Technology (ADAPT) Army Technology Objective (ATO)

Following the proof of concept work in EHF, and as a consequence of guidance from the Army Science Board, STCD initiated the ADAPT ATO to further develop SATCOM OTM antenna technology. During the approval process ADAPT was merged into the Tactical Network and Communication Antennas (TNCA) ATO.

The ADAPT ATO was geared to develop solutions that would meet size, weight, and power (SWAP) constraints for PM WIN-T and reduce SATCOM OTM positioner costs. The ADAPT products were as follows:

A low-cost Ku/Ka OTM antenna. This low profile dish based antenna system significantly reduced the SWaP and cost required for SATCOM OTM in two frequency bands. Technology advances allowed the required tracking performance to be achieved without the use of an external TALIN Attitude Heading Reference System (AHRS).

A low-profile, single-beam antenna. The low-profile, single-beam antenna was an effort to reduce the antenna height of reflector-based solutions. The antenna design employed a single-line array and a rexolite lens material to achieve necessary beam forming in a package under 8 inches high and 38 inches in diameter. This antenna also had the advantage of carrying both Ku and Ka transceiver chains and allowing the user to select the operating band electronically. This is a cooperative effort with the Office of Naval Research (ONR) and was contracted to Millitech in FY2007 and would produce three prototypes in late FY2009.

An X-band point of presence (PoP). This antenna was contracted to DRS Codem in FY2006. The goal was to create affordable X-band OTM antennas with the same SWaP and cost constraints as the low-cost Ku/Ka OTM antenna. The intent of this development was to examine OTM performance on the emerging X-band satellites such as XTAR and WGS.

Ku- and Ka-band power amplifiers. Higher power added efficiency (PAE) power amplifiers would provide greater output power while also reducing heat burden on an antenna system. The power amplifiers will use innovative technologies such as spatial combining or high power metamorphic high electron mobility transistor carriers to increase output power. Both Ku- and Ka-band power amplifiers will be developed and be compatible with the low cost PoP. Power Amplifiers (PA) developed under this ATO also may leverage the Army Research Laboratory’s work with Gallium Nitride and Metamorphic High Electron Mobility Transistor technologies to increase PA efficiency.

ADAPT had a very successful conclusion. The low-cost Ku/Ka OTM performance and unit production cost made it an attractive antenna. It was subsequently selected by PM WIN-T for the Increment 2 OTM Soldier Network Extension (SNE) requirements for lower echelons. Figure 3 shows the resultant antenna.

Figure 3, ADAPT Low-cost Ku/Ka OTM Antenna System

C. Affordable Low Profile Satellite (ALPS) Communications On the Move ATO

The ALPS ATO continues the development efforts described before. ALPS is a four year program, FY09 to FY12, to develop low profile and affordable antenna systems for Directional and Satellite Communications (SATCOM) on-the-move (OTM) to meet current and future force cost, SWaP, and performance requirements. Antennas for SATCOM OTM applications will be developed utilizing the widest bandwidths possible while maintaining adequate antenna gain, low visual signature, disciplined side-lobes, directivity, and pointing accuracy. Technologies will be developed for use in current and future military frequency bands (X, Ku, Ka and Q bands). There are 6 projects in the ALPS ATO:

Low-Profile, Single-Beam Antenna: This is a continuation of the ADAPT Low-Profile, Single-Beam Antenna described above.

Low Profile, Multi Band, K/Ka/Q Antenna System: The K/Ka/Q antenna system is a very low profile (6 inch objective) high performance system with a single transmit beam, a single receive beam and an optional second, fully independent receive beam. This system supports Ka and Q bands for transmit and K band for receive. All required equipment to support all bands will be included in the basic terminal design. Band changing will be fully electronically controlled.

Low Profile, Multi Band, X/K/Ka Antenna System: The X/K/Ka antenna system is a low profile system, with single transmit and receive beams. This antenna system will support communications over both X and Ka bands on the Wideband Global SATCOM (WGS) satellite.

Integrated Ka/Q Band Power Amplifier: The integrated Ka/Q band power amplifier will be developed as a form, fit, and function replacement for the appropriate antenna.

This power amplifier will provide operation in both frequency bands and at a high power added efficiency.

Small Aperture BFT Antenna: The small BFT antenna provides a migration path for the FBCB2/BFT system into frequency bands supported by military satellites (i.e., X). This antenna provides a small form factor and price point for high density fielding.

Table 2 lists a few key performance metrics of the 6 projects.

ALPS Project	Performance Metrics	Current	ALPS Project Objectives	Army Objectives
Low-profile, single-beam (Ku/Ka) antenna	Unit cost Form Factor Throughput G/T	\$135k (gimbal) 17"x26"x 26" 256/1544 kbps 11/12 dB-K	\$125k (hybrid) 8in x 38 in dia 512/1544 kbps >12/12 dB-K	\$75k 6in x 30 in dia 512/1544 kbps >12/12 dB-K
Low-profile, multi-band K/Ka/Q antenna	Unit cost Form Factor Throughput	\$400k 12"x40"x40" 512/1544 kbps	\$150k 6"x24"x36" 1544kbps	\$150k 6"x24"x36" 1544kbps
Integrated Ka/Q power amp	Unit cost Power eff Form Factor	\$25k 24%(Ka)/15%(Q) 70cu in/20lbs	\$12k >25% 30 cu. in/8.5 lb	\$10k >25% 30 cu. in/8.5 lb
Low-profile multi-band X/K/Ka antenna	Unit cost Form Factor Throughput	>\$250k 20" diameter 256kbps (single band)	\$125k 12" diameter 1544kbps (dual band)	\$100k 12" diameter 1544kbps (dual band)
Small aperture BFT	Unit cost Form Factor Throughput	\$5k (L-band) 8"x8"x6" 2.4kbps	\$5-10k (Ka or X) 8"x8"x6" 32kbps	\$5k (Ka or X) 8"x8"x6" 64kbps
C/Ku Affordable Direct Antenna	First Unit Cost	\$200K	\$75K	<\$75K

Table 2. Key Performance Metrics

The objectives for these projects are challenging. Some of the areas of investigation which could potentially provide solutions for the ALPS projects to meet their objectives:

- Develop low-profile technologies such as hybrid scan, slotted arrays, continuous transverse stub, and phased array apertures to reduce SWaP.
- Develop technologies for phased array elements, multiple beam pointing and steering, and smaller RF components to achieve simultaneous transmission capability in a very small form factor.
- Explore higher power and wider band gap amplifier technologies including Gallium Nitride, Metamorphic High Electron Mobility Transistor (mHEMT) to create a dual-band and high efficiency power amplifier.
- Develop lower cost antenna pointing technologies such as micro electro mechanical systems (MEMS) gyros/sensors and leverage AMRDEC

- Leverage antenna technologies: Small Aperture X-Band SBIR Phase II, and DARPA 3-D Micro Electromagnetic Radio Frequency Systems (3D MERFS) Program to develop Blue Force Tracking (BFT) antennas in military bands.

The technologies developed by the ALPS ATO are expected to be transition to various Army Program of Records in order to reduce some of their technology risks and to facilitate meeting future requirements.

- Low-profile, single beam (Ku/Ka) antenna to PM WIN-T, FY11
- Integrated Ka/Q-band power amplifier to PM WIN-T HC3, FY13
- Low-profile, multi-band K/Ka/Q antenna to PM WIN-T, FY13
- Low-profile, multi-band X/K/Ka antenna to PM WIN-T, FY 12
- Small aperture BFT antenna to PM FBCB2, FY12
- C/Ku Affordable Directional Antenna to PM WIN-T, FY13

D. Next Generation SATCOM OTM

The next generation ATO addressing SATCOM OTM technology gaps is envisioned to take SATCOM OTM to the next level. Objective requirements will be supported such as supporting more integration into future vehicles resulting in very little space utilized and very low observable profile, the ultimate solution being a conformal antenna utilizing the infrastructure of the vehicle. Scalable and separable apertures will be developed in order to ease integration and provide the best performance in the space available using standardized building blocks. Efforts are envisioned to be multi-beam, multi-band antenna systems with excellent performance. DTUPC will continue to be a focus.

E. Supporting Technology Initiatives

Early on it became apparent that there were many technical hurdles to be addressed if low cost tactical on-the-move SATCOM was to become a reality. The earliest problem areas included the controller, phased shifter and attitude and heading reference system cost and performance. Later problem areas included the high power dissipation of power amplifiers and low noise amplifiers as well as the need for advanced cooling systems.

All of these efforts have been or are currently being addressed. The initial controller for on-the-move systems

utilized a VME chassis and cost over \$50K. This was accompanied by a \$>50K Honeywell Tactical Advanced Land Inertial Navigator (TALIN). A dual use application program for low cost X-Band phased arrays (Harris Corp) developed a low cost PC-104 controller, which cut controller costs to \$5K and resulted in a considerable SWaP savings. The TALIN replacement has been an ongoing effort with Enpoint, LLC, which started as a SBIR and continued thru additional development. The result is Pinpoint, which in its final form will provide a heading accuracy of 0.1 degree and is estimated to cost <\$5K thanks to the use of MEMS sensors and coherent GPS.

Phase shifters are a problem area all to themselves. They are the single most costly element (\$50-150 ea) in the phased arrays STCD has developed to date. The solution was a Manufacturing Technology Program for both Ferroelectric (Agile RF) and MEMS phase shifters (Raytheon). These three year programs have resulted in the development of volume production facilities that can produce phase shifters at frequencies from X-Band through Q-Band at a cost of <\$10 each in production quantities.

The power added efficiency of commercial power amplifiers at Ku and Ka bands was found to be inadequate for on-the-move systems, where a sealed radome is required to protect the antenna system against the harsh tactical military environment. A contract was let to Wavestream to develop high efficiency power amplifiers at both Ku and Ka Bands. These amplifiers were to be form, fit and function equivalent to the commercial amplifiers initially utilized in our Ku/Ka on-the-move antenna system concurrently developed by L-3 Datron. Wavestream increased the linear power by 4 dB at Ku band. The Ka band amplifier is still under development.

STCD has recently begun development of a 30 GHz, 10 watt GaN power amplifier with Hittite under a SBIR program. This amplifier is expected to have a PAE >30% and will lead to additional developments at Ka and Q bands. Along with these initiative, the Army will leverage DARPA efforts in GaN, upon a successful release process at Ka band (far term Q band), we will initiate a development program to build a GaN based SSPA.

On the move SATCOM provides an extensive capability to the warfighter, adding a new dimension to transformational forces communications architecture. With the launch of WGS and AEHF satellites, there will be capacity to support larger scale OTM networks. The antenna systems are desired to have smaller footprints. Typically trades are done with the aspect ratio of the antenna systems resulting in a reduced sized reflector and

higher power PA, while trying to balance system integrity with regards to regulatory requirements. Although designing a reflector and feed system at Ka & Q band presents its own challenges, the bigger challenge to date has been in the power amplifier technology. A significant reduction in footprint requires an increase in power density and close attention to thermal management. The Army has on going technology initiatives investigating high power density & high power added efficiency Ka & Q band MMIC GaAs devices. These programs have taken existing Ka & Q band GaAs based MMIC designs and pushed the power and efficiency envelope. Thus far the program has successfully produced Ka & Q band MMIC amplifiers and yielding approximately 4.4W at a Power Added Efficiency (PAE) of 25% and approximately 4W at a PAE of 20%, respectively. These are being integrated into a small form factor Solid State Power Amplifier (SSPA).

When one considers that current low noise amplifiers draw only ~250 milliwatts, it is hard to realize that they lead to a phased array with excessive power dissipation. Such was the case with a 512 element dual beam K Band array developed by Harris. It required a 1 kW heat exchanger. We now have low noise amplifiers with power dissipations of 25 to 50 milliwatts with state-of-the-art noise figures under development by Custom MMIC Design Services under another SBIR program. The low dissipation and high performance of these amplifiers will allow the design and fabrication of receive arrays with >4000 elements with modest cooling systems.

Cooling systems are an important aspect of system design and reliability, but are often an afterthought in antenna system design. STCD has three new SBIR programs which offer the promise of much higher cooling efficiencies than we have achieved in present systems. Creare is developing a high efficiency phased array cooling system with advanced cross flow blowers and a heat pipe cold plate. Aspen systems is developing a high efficiency refrigeration based cooling system for cooling our current dish antenna systems. Lastly, Technology Applications, Inc is developing a similar high efficiency refrigeration based cooling system for phased arrays.

All of these component technology efforts have been carefully selected and pursued for their contributions to performance and cost reduction for required antenna systems.

COLLABORATION AND SYSTEM EFFORTS

A persistent theme from the discussions above is the emphasis on affordability. There is a constant drive to create technical solutions that are not only better, but

cheaper. This is due to the reality of a cost-constrained Army. Programs of Record cannot accept a technological development when the unit cost is prohibitive, since program budgets are fixed.

So too the Army science and technology budget is cost constrained and fixed. Research and development programs must work within limited funding while facing significant challenges. One mitigation has been successful partnering with other organizations. An example is the low-profile, single-beam antenna.

The ADAPT/ALPS low-profile, single-beam antenna is a cooperative effort between CERDEC S&TCD and the Office of Naval Research (ONR). ONR Code 30 supports USMC expeditionary forces that have OTM challenges similar to the Army. This common cause led STCD and ONR to enact a memorandum of agreement in May 2007 to jointly fund this development. Under the MOA both organizations participate in the formulation of requirements, monitor performance (with Army leading and having contracting responsibility), and will cooperatively test the prototypes upon delivery.

The single-beam antenna also gives example to collaborate with a transition partner. PM WIN-T has shown interest in the low-profile, single-beam antenna and attends technical reviews. The interest also has extended to adding funding to the contract.

Collaboration has not been solely a fiduciary activity. The similarities of requirements discovered while establishing the MOA above had lead to STCD and ONR collaborating by knowledge sharing and in lending expertise to each other's efforts. Another example is STCD monitoring ONR development of two separate X-band OTM antennas for USMC situational awareness and communications.

MIL-STD-188-164B INITIATIVES

Since the X-band payload on the Wideband Global SATCOM (WGS) satellites are significantly more powerful than the Defense Satellite Communications System (DSCS) satellites they are replacing, STCD started investigating the potential of using X-band for SATCOM OTM. There are significant potential advantages for X-band SATCOM OTM, including higher capacity than commercial L-band, and a greater weather robustness than Ku or Ka-band given the same satellite resources. The interference issue is potentially less than in the commercial Ku-band due to a greater average angular separation between geo-stationary satellites, and the use of military satellites represents a great potential recurring cost savings over commercial satellites.

However, before a terminal is permitted to operate on the WGS constellation, it has to go through a terminal certification process to show that it complies with MIL-STD 188-164, "Interoperability of SHF Satellite Communications Earth Terminals." The current version of MIL-STD 188-164 does not have a terrestrial OTM terminal class, so in parallel with the development of the ADAPT X-band OTM antenna, STCD started analysis in support of developing the necessary changes to the MIL-STD so that these changes could be inserted during the current revision cycle [11]. Our analysis efforts are continuing, and have expanded to include examination of the issues and implications of moving the Blue Force Tracking (BFT) function to WGS X-band.

TRANSITION OF TECHNOLOGIES TO THE TACTICAL ARMY

Our technology development efforts typically result in a prototype that is then available for testing and demonstration. Because a transition partner is identified early, a successful technology will typically be turned over to a program of record for production. Any final system changes and logistics efforts would be accomplished under the program of record. Programs of record like WIN-T are providing the SATCOM OTM solutions for the tactical Army, and our technology efforts will continue to target their requirements and identified technology gaps.

SUMMARY

SATCOM OTM technology initiatives were outlined in this paper. CERDEC S&TCD has provided and will continue to provide successful SATCOM OTM solutions for the tactical Army, supporting a non-contiguous battlefield OTM. Inter-related technical hurdles are analyzed and specific technologies are targeted to support system performance requirements and attain production cost goals. Current efforts are supporting technical challenges within known constraints and future efforts will target upcoming objectives to include a more integrated approach within the infrastructure of new vehicles. CERDEC S&TCD will continue to partner with our Joint Services as well as other technical agencies to leverage resources to achieve the most technical advances possible and continue to successfully transition developed technology to programs of record for fielding.

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